

Driving activity assessment using accelerometer data

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Abstract. In this paper, we evaluated a variety of features acquired from data recorded from single tri-axial accelerometer placed on the subjects' wrist in order to differentiate among driving events. Results obtained from 12 experienced drivers assessed in driving simulators with wristband revealed features that might be relevant for future driver's activity recognition. Our preliminary exploratory data analysis showed that the most informative features for discriminative analysis among driving tasks are entropy and average spectral energy of the resultant acceleration.

Keywords—accelerometer, activity recognition, driving simulator, exploratory data analysis, hand movements

1 Introduction

Driving is an activity with significant health risks if the driver's psychological or physiological state is not at sufficiently good level. Due to the possible severity of consequences caused by driving accidents, it is of great importance to detect possible causes and their implications. Driving simulations are useful assessment tools with the ability to put drivers in simulated and dangerous situations without real risk involved. To quantify driver's profile parameters and behavior, various measurements of physiological signals were proposed previously. [1]

The main hypothesis of this research was that different parts of the driving simulation can be discerned by analysis of recorded data. Specifically, the focus of this study was on the data analysis collected from the single tri-axial accelerometer during simulation, in order to quantify and analyze driver's activity. This idea is supported by the results obtained from human activity recognition studies by application of accelerometers, where relatively high classification accuracy of above 88% was achieved [2-8].

The aim of this study was to explore a variety of features for the differentiation among driving simulation tasks and phases. Several carefully selected features were extracted from accelerometer data placed on subjects' wrist. We concluded that the most promising features might be entropy and average spectral energy of the resultant acceleration.

2 Methods and materials

2.1 Data set

Data used in this study is collected with E4 sensor wristband (Empatica Inc., Cambridge, USA) during the simulation in driving simulator (Nervtech TM, Trzin, Slovenia) at the University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Electrical Engineering in Slovenia. Beside acceleration, sensor wristband records volume pulse, galvanic skin response, skin temperature, inter-beat intervals, and heart rate. For this study, we used only acceleration data for analysis.

Data set was obtained from 12 participants with more than two years driving experience. Each subject completed one of the driving scenarios: highway drive (9 subjects completed this scenario), countryside drive (two subjects), and city drive (one subject). In this study, we used only highway scenario, since the majority of subjects completed this driving simulation. The Nervtech scenarios used here (SANJOSE, Nervtech, Trzin, Slovenia) had different events, tasks, and scenery. All scenarios were divided into different parts termed tasks. Each task is described with numbers in the range of -1 to 13, where number -1 indicates an unclassified task and tasks from 0 to 13 indicate different unique parts of the track. A scenario does not necessarily contain all tasks. Each scenario contains only specific tasks from 0 to 13 (e.g. highway scenario consists of tasks -1, 8, 9, 12, and 13). Each task is further divided into phases annotated by numbers in the range of 0 to 3, where 0 indicates the initial uneventful driving phase, 1 indicates the driving phase, 2 indicates the preparation phase, and 3 indicates the action phase. A task does not necessarily contain all phases. The most interesting part of the analysis is the phase 3. This is the part where collisions can happen (e.g. children suddenly cross the road).

Used data set consists of 12 files (for each subject) with complete data collected from E4 wristband and video recordings of the driver's vision field. Video recordings were available for only three subjects. Data of interest extracted from the files includes: (1) unix time stamp, (2) scenario name, (3) task number, (4) phase number, and (5) accelerometer data from x -axis, y -axis, and z -axis.

All subjects signed informed consents. The study was performed in accordance with the Code of ethics and Guidelines for studies involving human subjects of University of Ljubljana, that follow recommendations of Helsinki Declaration.

2.2 Data transformation and preprocessing

All processing steps were performed in R [9], using R Studio IDE (Rstudio, Inc., Boston, USA) and official CRAN network (The Comprehensive R Archive Network) with up-to-date libraries for R programming language. The following CRAN packages/libraries were used: dplyr [10], ggplot2 [11], signal [12], and entropy [13].

Raw data transformations and accelerometer data preprocessing steps were necessary to convert the data into a more suitable form for feature extraction. Time stamps were transformed from *unix* format into seconds. Accelerometer data for three axes were transformed into a function of gravitational acceleration (g). Resulting signals were in the range $[-2g, 2g]$.

Fig. 1. Basic boxplots of features for tasks from the highway drive scenario. Features ar_ent and $energy$ were selected as the promising separators of the classes by visual inspection by two experienced researchers. The criteria for the selection was minimization of overlap between boxplots of different tasks. Please, see Table 1 for details and features description.

Since acceleration was not recorded with a fixed sampling frequency, accelerometer data needed to be resampled using time stamps. Data was up-sampled using cubic spline interpolation so that the number of samples in the resampled data was equal to the number of annotations related to tasks and phases. Resulting sample rate varied and was in range of [46.6, 53.5] Hz.

Acceleration data consists of the two independent components: one is caused by linear hand movement, and the other is gravity acceleration. Those components were necessary for the later analysis and needed to be separated. As shown in [2,7], gravity component can be reliably approximated by low pass filtering. For this purpose, a 4th order Butterworth filter with cutoff frequency of 0.35 Hz (following the range suggested in [2]) was applied. Linear acceleration was taken as an original signal filtered with 4th order high pass Butterworth filter with cutoff set at 0.35 Hz, and then 4th order low pass Butterworth filter with cutoff frequency of 6 Hz. Lastly, filtered individual linear acceleration data from three axis (vectors a_x , a_y , and a_z) is combined to form a resultant acceleration vector a_r :

$$a_r = \sqrt{a_x^2 + a_y^2 + a_z^2} \quad (1)$$

The resulting signal a_r calculated from Eq. (1) does not depend on the orientation of the accelerometer, and as such is more suitable for this study.

2.3 Feature extraction

After data preparation, we calculated features. The majority of the features were previously exploited in human activity recognition studies [2-10]. Acceleration signal a_r was segmented by task and phase annotations, and then the segments of the same class were merged together.

Table 1. Selected features

Feature	Description, [units]
standard deviation (SD) of a_r (ar_sd)	Activity quantifier, rectifies negative acceleration, reduces gravity influence, used in [2-8], [$g\ m/s^2$]
absolute maximum value of a_r (ar_max)	Potentially good indicator of critical situations where fast rephases are required, used in [3], [$g\ m/s^2$]
Shannon entropy of a_r (ar_ent)	Degree of randomness, higher value is expected at situations that demand intervention, used in [3, 6], [a.u.]
zero-crossing rate of a_r (ar_zcr)	Good periodicity and high frequency content estimator, increases with activity, used in [4], [a.u.]
SD of the first derivative of roll angle ($dtheta_sd$)	Rotation angle around the axis perpendicular to the wheel plane, SD of its first derivative, indicator of turnings, [rad/s]
average spectral energy density of a_r ($energy$)	Carries the information about periodicity and energy, used in [5,6], [$g^2(m/s^2)^2$]. Please, see text for more details.

Features were calculated for the merged segments that are longer than 2 s. All features with a short description are given in Table 1.

SD (ar_sd) is calculated as mean squared difference between the samples and the mean value of the signal, with Bessel's correction. Feature ar_max is calculated as the absolute maximum value of the signal a_r in time domain. Shannon entropy (ar_ent) of the acceleration signal was calculated as:

Fig. 2. Basic boxplots of features by phase. Features *ar_ent* and *energy* were selected as appropriate separators by visual inspection by two experienced researchers. The criteria for the selection was minimization of overlap between boxplots of different classes. Additionally, more significance is given to the distinction of phase 3, because it indicates a critical event. See Table 1 for details and feature description.

$$H(a_r) = -\sum p(a_r) \log_2(p(a_r)) \quad (2)$$

Values $p(a_r)$ were obtained as probabilities of each level of the signal a_r discretized by amplitude into 32 levels. Zero-crossing rate of the signal (*ar_zcr*) was calculated as the number of sign changes of the signal in time domain normalized by the length of the signal in samples. Roll angle used for calculating SD of the first derivative of the roll angle (*dtheta_sd*) is estimated based on approximated gravity components g_x , g_y , and g_z as shown in [14], by using the following equation:

$$\theta = \arctan\left(\frac{g_z}{\sqrt{g_x^2 + g_y^2}}\right) \quad (3)$$

Average spectral energy density (*energy*) was calculated as the mean of the squared FFT coefficients of a_r . If FFT of a signal has prominent peaks (indicating periodicity), then squaring FFT coefficients would emphasize the energy of the peaks. Hence, higher *energy* indicates higher periodicity for the given frequency range. This feature was previously used to differentiate between walking and running [5, 6].

3 Results

Quality of the class separation for each feature is evaluated by observing basic boxplots for each feature with tasks and phases as groups (Figs. 1-2). Based on the information from Figs. 1-2, we selected *ar_ent* and *energy* of acceleration signal as features that distinguish classes in the appropriate way (minimization of overlap between boxplots of different classes) for both tasks and phases. For phases, we paid special attention to isolate phase 3 as good as possible,

as it indicates a critical event. Scatter plots that represent class localization based on the selected features are shown in Fig. 3. Additionally, selected features are plotted in time domain by windowing the acceleration signal a_r with 3 s

Fig. 3. Figures show distribution of feature pairs (*energy*, *ar_ent*) grouped by tasks (top) and phases (bottom), for highway scenario.

Fig. 4. Values of the selected features normalized by maximum in time domain for the city scenario, along with frames from the corresponding video recording at critical time points (moments before and after collision). Annotation lines are given below the graph, where the top line represents phase for the given time point, while the bottom line refers to the current task.

window duration, and calculating these features for each window for the city scenario (please, see Fig. 4). We added this figure in order to get more insight into the dynamics of the selected features and its relation to simulation events.

4 Discussion and conclusions

The final results concerning identification of simulation scenario parts are not satisfying (Fig. 3). For both tasks and phases, classes significantly overlap. We expected that phases would be more separable than tasks, due to fact that the phases are related to the driving dynamic, while tasks are not necessarily separable. If we had taken into consideration all scenarios, the separability would be even worse in both cases due to the larger number of tasks.

To be fair, chosen visualization method with only two features is rather harsh, but there are also other problems. In the process of feature evaluation, we saw that none of the features, although commonly used in similar studies with success, have shown good discrimination. There are some possible reasons for this. By inspecting video recordings and comparing events with features, we concluded that participants reacted differently (e.g. performing exceptionally well in a critical situation - phase 3, but making an accident in a seemingly calm situation- phases 0-2). These assumptions are further supported by boxplots in Figs. 1-2, where variability in features corresponds to larger interquartile width. There is also a problem with the subjective data labeling (e.g. Fig. 4 shows the situation in the video that we deemed as critical, but it was marked as phase 2, while the other, more comfortable parts were marked as phase 3). Further, *energy* shows good responsiveness to accident despite possible erroneous annotations (Fig. 4).

Using the accelerometer placed on a wrist in order to recognize driving situations is still relatively new and improvements are needed. It has a potential at least as a support to the more established driver profiling methods. For future work, we will include all data from E4 wrist band from a larger sample. Since we used only subjective criteria to select the most appropriate features (visual inspection), our future work should also include more objective approach based on statistical methods. Given the participants' demographics, we would try to further inspect the potential regularities that could exist between different driver groups.

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